

The COREnect Editorial

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Dear Readers of our COREnect newsletter,

The COREnect team is taking action to build a map of strategic technology for the European Commission. We want to help guide the EC to ensure we have enough technological and industrial sovereignty for electronics to continue to thrive as we storm through the coming 10 years of 5G developments and all preparing for 6G. I want to thank all COREnect partners, the experts, and all individuals who commit valuable time to generate the anticipated outcome. The vision and mission are ambitious.

I am very proud of the team and happy to see such progress in 2020. We have started all 3 expert groups and have delivered a first vision of the necessary work ahead.

Once again, a huge thank you to the team and the experts, as well as to the EC, for having to trust us in this honorable task.